
Recommendation #1

Title: Plan the feedback and structure it before its delivery.

Evidences: MLR G2, G13, G16

Interviews I4: *"I think that when you can have a prior feedback agenda you can estimate much better with the time you have, how much time to spend on each item on the prior agenda"*
I7: *"Get organized beforehand. Don't think about something bad that the person did and ask for feedback. Get organized beforehand, try to also reflect on the good things that person has before you go, and point the finger at that specific point. And then at that specific point, it's what I told you: get organized, think about what happened, and how you can give examples and not just criticize. Think about how to give the person tips to improve."*
I9: *"When I'm going to give feedback, I usually take my notebook and write it down, then I write a little text of what I want to tell the person about the positive points, what can be improved, why, I look for examples and write them down there too."*

Survey 2 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified in the following quotes:
P57: *"Something more structured, viewed by topics, to have a good overview of everything."*
P72: *"Define in advance what will be evaluated, the people who will participate, and prepare so that everyone has time to think about HOW they will communicate the feedback."*

Recommendation #2

Title: Define the evaluative rule and calibrate it.

Evidences: MLR G8, G11

Interviews I3: *"Today I realize that with the performance cycle and the company's values very well-defined, we can identify some aspects and some skills that are already right for you to evaluate. (...) Also understand what level is expected for that person, because it is very different for you to give feedback to an intern who has just joined and to another who is preparing to become a junior."*

Survey 28 participants mentioned they would like to have a previous definition of the evaluated points, and 9 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified in the following quotes:
P15: *"Not knowing exactly what is expected. Sometimes, it is very subjective when it is said."*
P76: *"The company has to present how its feedback culture works, so that leaders and other employees better understand the evaluation criteria and, consequently, provide more truthful and engaged feedback."*

Recommendation #3

Title: Use multidimensional indicators to evaluate team members.

Evidences: MLR A13, A15, G3, G8, G9, G18, G20

Interviews I2: *"Those working directly with the person sometimes have a better view of the person's work. (...) then I talk to the person's peers, with the sponsor who works directly with the person, sometimes that person has*

leaders, and is acting as a mentor to an intern... So it will be talked to everyone around that person to be able to give feedback to that person.”
 I3: “What I think is cool about the feedback canvas, which the leader-leader feedback sometimes doesn't have, is the look of other people. So, in the feedback canvas, you find out that that person did that activity and was so collaborative with the other interns, and you didn't have that vision... So, sometimes having the vision of other people is significant.”

Survey 18 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified in the following quotes:
 P13: “When feedback is given out of obligation by a person who does not participate in my day-to-day work and therefore has no way of knowing exactly what I do.”
 P58: “Feedback from peers, something like that, naturally. A culture focused on this, but it should be done organically and not just because it is mandatory.”

Recommendation #4

Title: Keep the feedback regular.

Evidences: **MLR** A4, G3, G4, G6, G7, G8, G10, G11, G13, G14, G15, G16, G18, G20

Interviews I8: “One very important thing I think is that you do not lose your timing, you know? If I have a performance cycle in 1 month and I have the opportunity to give feedback now, I don't need to wait, because once you lose your timing I don't think it makes any sense to talk about it again.”

Survey 30 participants mentioned they would like the interval between feedback sessions to be reduced, and 16 recommended the feedback to be regular and continuous, as exemplified in the quotes below:
 P4: “Maintain the routine of providing feedback every determined period, and not only when there is a need for improvements.”
 P38: “Have a regular frequency of feedback, and not just when something happens or very sporadically.”

Recommendation #5

Title: Provide objective feedback, with examples and clear orientations.

Evidences: **MLR** A15, A16, G1, G3, G5, G6, G7, G8, G9, G12, G14, G15, G17, G19

Interviews I1: “When someone sees that you have material, and you give examples of what not to do, of how it could have been done better, I think it's pleasant for the person receiving it because generic or very vague feedback is terrible, I don't think it improves anything.”
 I2: “Not only criticize but also say what was expected, like: “Look, I think you didn't do what was expected, you should have done it this way”. When you give constructive criticism the way we do, we don't say “You were bad at that”, we say “You can improve on that if you do it this way” or “You did this, but you should have done it this way”. So when the feedback is well constructed, with instructions on what the person has to do to improve, I think it is very positive.”
 I9: “Feedback has to be concise, so we have to be careful when we are talking to someone because, by the end of the day, it's their career. So, you must always be careful not to beat around the bush, because they might interpret what you are saying differently. So, it has to be concise, direct, and that's not always easy.”
 I10: “For feedback to be good, for it to have some results, it has to have the inputs, the situations, the examples, you know? Because if I go to an

employee and say: “Look, your productivity has dropped!”, he’ll say “Why are you saying that? Based on what?”, right? So I think I have to take the inputs for the feedback, to be able to have positive feedback, to be able to have results, you know? [The lack of examples] can give room for him to think that it’s his manager’s opinion, right? Some people might think it’s something personal “What’s he saying this based on? I don’t see that, so why is he saying that?”, so I think that also opens up that gap.”

Survey 16 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified by the quotes below:
P6: “I think it’s important that the feedback emphasizes a problem that needs to be worked on, that is, it is objective and oriented towards what the individual wants. The leadership must say objectively the points that need to be worked on, and how far the individual is from reaching his goal. Be that point a soft skill, hard skill, or a set of concrete factors.”
P60: “Written and detailed feedback (examples of something you did/do) is better for understanding how to improve; (...) Suggestions on how to improve something are better than just pointing out the error.”

Recommendation #6

Title: Balance positive and negative points during feedback.

Evidences: Interviews 17: “It is well learned here that we always have to give feedback, weighing good and bad things to improve. I like to highlight 3 good points, that the person is doing super well, and 3 points that the person has to improve, and that’s usually the way I consolidate.”
19: “When I’m going to give feedback, I usually take my notebook and write it down, then I write a little text of what I want to tell the person about the positive points, what can be improved, why it needs to be improved, I look for examples and write them down there too.”

Survey 6 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified by the quotes below:
P17: “I believe that for good feedback, it is necessary to say what points are good and what needs improvement.”
P60: “Create a healthy feedback practice, sandwich style feedback where the message is conveyed delicately.”

Recommendation #7

Title: Provide a tangible goal-oriented development plan.

Evidences: MLR A16, G4, G5, G8, G11, G18

Interviews 12: “It’s even necessary to control the team so as not to put too much in the plan because you have to think about the long-term things you’re going to do in 6 months. Sometimes the person gets a lot of stuff excited about the feedback and ends up getting lost.”

Survey 46 participants mentioned they would like to build a development plan after feedback, and 4 mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified below:
P4: “Create a career plan and gradually update it during the sessions.”
P5: “Develop an activity plan based on feedback.”

Recommendation #8

Title: Create a trusted environment for feedback delivery.

Evidences: MLR A1, G6, G13, G19

- Interviews** I2: *“Have an open and trustworthy communication channel, so that the person knows that they will not be judged for what they said in 1:1, they will not be punished for what they said in 1:1, they have to have space to be able to talk.”*
 I4: *“I think that feedback is a process, despite being formal and that we adopt daily, it also has a bit of affinity with the person you are talking to. Having a good interpersonal relationship often results in giving more assertive feedback, (...) knowing how to speak better, knowing what the person's real difficulties are.”*
 I6: *“Employees need to feel that they have a representative, but that doesn't mean that person is on another level and distant. It's necessary to ensure that each person has the freedom and feels comfortable to raise their hand when necessary.”*
 I8: *“[Feedback] It's a lot about understanding how people work, at the very least, to always try to establish a dialogue that makes them feel comfortable, makes them feel open to talking about everything.”*
- Survey** 4 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified by the quotes below:
 P44: *“Creating an environment where people feel safe making mistakes is essential, otherwise feedback will be shallow.”*
 P73: *“Fostering a relationship of respect and trust between leaders and those they lead.”*

Recommendation #9

Title: Use feedback to recognize and reward team members.

Evidences: **MLR** G1, G8, G11, G15, G20

Interviews I7: *“Regarding the positive aspects, reinforcements are also important. Don't wait until the end to say if the person did well, we'll give feedback right then and there. Sometimes there's an analyst or someone a little more junior who does well during the presentation, so I'll say “Congratulations, you did well!” because it motivates and consolidates.”*

Survey 4 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified by the quotes below:
 P9: *“I also believe that good results should always be rewarded in some individually relevant (personalized) way.”*
 P32: *“Continuous and encouraging feedback, not just for the big things, but for the small day-to-day victories.”*

Recommendation #10

Title: Request a return feedback from team members.

Evidences: **Interviews** I7: *“I ask ‘How do you think I could do better...’ because sometimes the person's performance is because of my leadership.”*
 I10: *“Always, even in informal feedback, I always ask for feedback in return. This is important to me, and I have already received feedback on impressive things. (...) Then see what a cool thing: I had an action that for me was a neutral thing, and people understood it differently. (...) I think this return feedback is very interesting because there are things that we don't imagine, there are actions that we don't imagine are being misinterpreted.”*

Survey 4 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified by the quotes below:
 P10: *“I do not like the absence of feedback or when it is not bilateral. The manager must be evaluated by the team as well.”*

P36: *“Openness to clarification of the points of view of those who give and receive feedback”*

Recommendation #11

Title: Do a constant feedback follow-up.

Evidences: **MLR** A1, A4, A16, G5, G9, G18

Survey 14 participants mentioned this recommendation, as exemplified by the quotes below:

P14: *“Receive specific feedback and have a subsequent follow-up on the points discussed.”*

P37: *“For me, maintaining a linear form of feedback would be better, always talking about all the points mentioned previously so we can see an evolutionary line.”*
